

EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN: CONCEPT, GOALS, TYPES, APPROXIMATE PLANNING

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Abstract. As we know that the extracurricular activities of schoolchildren are a set of all types of schoolchildren's activities, in which, in accordance with the main educational program of an educational institution, the tasks of education and socialization, development of interests, and the formation of universal educational activities are solved. Extracurricular activities are an integral part of the educational process at school and allow you to fully implement the requirements of the federal state educational standard of primary general education. In this work the features of this component of the educational process are providing students with the opportunity of a wide range of activities aimed at their development is considered; as well as the process of filling extracurricular activities with specific content is studied.

Keywords: extracurricular education, educational disciplines, learning problems, extracurricular activities teaching technologies,

INTRODUCTION

Extracurricular activities of schoolchildren are a set of all types of schoolchildren's activities, in which, in accordance with the main educational program of an educational institution, the tasks of education and socialization, development of interests, and the formation of universal educational activities are solved. Extracurricular activities are an integral part of the educational process at school and allow you to fully implement the requirements of the federal state educational standard (FSES) of primary general education. The features of this component of the educational process are providing students with the opportunity of a wide range of activities aimed at their development; as well as the independence of the educational institution in the process of filling extracurricular activities with specific content.

The purpose of extracurricular activities is to assist in ensuring the achievement of the planned results of mastering the basic educational program of primary general education (personal, meta-subject, subject) by students in grades 1-4. Creation of an educational environment that ensures the activation of social, intellectual interests of students in their free time, the development of a healthy, creatively growing personality, with a formed civic responsibility and legal self-awareness, prepared for life in new conditions, capable of socially significant practical activities, the implementation of volunteer initiatives.

The main tasks of education at the present stage of development of our society are: the inclusion of students in versatile activities; creation of conditions for the implementation of the main educational goals; optimization of the study load of students; formation of abilities for successful socialization in society, education of diligence, ability to overcome difficulties, purposefulness and perseverance in achieving results. According to the requirements of the Educational Standard of primary general education, extracurricular activities are organized in the following areas of personality development (*sports and recreation, spiritual and moral, social, general intellectual, general cultural*).

Extracurricular activities can be organized according to the following types of activities: gaming, cognitive, leisure and entertainment activities (leisure communication), problem-value communication; artistic creativity, social creativity (social transformative volunteering); technical creativity, labor (industrial) activity, sports and health-improving activities; tourism and local history activities.

The hours allotted for extracurricular activities are used at the request of students and are aimed at the implementation of various forms of its organization, different from the lesson system of education. Classes are held in the form of excursions, circles, sections, round tables, conferences, debates, KVN, quizzes, festive events, class hours, school scientific societies, competitions, research and scientific research, etc. By visiting circles and sections, students adapt perfectly to their peers, thanks to the individual work of the leader, the material is studied more deeply. In the classroom, leaders try to reveal in students such abilities as organizational, creative, musical, which plays an important role in the spiritual development of adolescents. Extracurricular activities should direct their activities to each student so that he can feel his uniqueness and relevance.

For the organization of extracurricular activities, forms other than classroom activities can be used, including extracurricular activities that may include individual lessons for a teacher with children who require psychological, pedagogical and correctional support (including individual lessons in the production of oral speech, handwriting and writing etc.), individual and group consultations (including remote ones) for children of various categories, etc.

The forms of organization of the educational process, the alternation of educational and extracurricular activities within the framework of the implementation of the main educational program of primary general education are determined by the educational institution. Extracurricular activities, as well as the activities of students within the framework of the lessons, are aimed at achieving the results of mastering the main educational program. But first of all, it is the achievement of personal and metasubject results. This also determines the specifics of extracurricular activities, during which the student not only and even not so much has to learn how to learn how to act, feel, make decisions, etc. The psychophysiological characteristics of a child of the seventh year of life (complexity of voluntary regulation of activity, rapid fatigue, etc.) lead to the fact that static loads, restrictions on the motor regime, rapid switching from one type of activity to another, etc. are difficult for children. In addition, for first-graders, the types of activities that they were engaged in in preschool childhood, primarily play activities are still very relevant. Therefore, the use of such forms of organization of the educational process as targeted walks, excursions, educational games, etc. is of particular importance for the formation of the ability to learn, and reliance on visual-effective and visual-figurative thinking will contribute to the formation of logical thinking at the first stages of schooling. The educational institution independently chooses the directions of extracurricular activities, determines the time frame (the number of hours for a certain type of activity). The content of classes provided for as part of extracurricular activities is formed taking into account the wishes of students and their parents (legal representatives). The main advantage of extracurricular activities is to provide students with the opportunity for a wide range of activities aimed at their development.

It is more efficient to organize extracurricular activities in the mode of activities of extended day groups, where walks, lunch, and then extracurricular activities are provided. Before self-training, it is better for students attending extended-day groups to organize walks, outdoor and

sports games, socially useful work at the site of a general educational institution, and after self-training - participation in emotional events.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The sports and recreational direction is realized through such forms as sports holidays and competitions, electives, circles (moving, folk, recreational games), children's sports sections, various types of sports and recreational activities. Spiritual and moral direction, a general cultural direction is realized through circles of artistic creativity, applied art: cross-stitch, stitch embroidery; patchwork plastic, soft toy; planar and volumetric floristry, collage; painting on stones, wood; paper plastic; cold batik; stained glass; work with skin straws, etc.; circles of technical creativity (lego - design), home crafts; visits to art exhibitions, museums, cinema, art festivals, performances in the classroom, school, theater; artistic actions of schoolchildren in the society surrounding the school. Games - miniatures, dramatization of plots from history, dialogues on topics, reading and watching colorful educational programs, computer games (specially selected by a specialist), playing an instrument, listening to music, etc.

The general intellectual direction is realized through such forms as cognitive conversations, subject electives "Informatics: Logic and Algorithms", "Information Technology", etc., "Children's Rhetoric", etc., circles "Journey to the Past", "Entertaining toponomy", etc., Olympiads, didactic theater, public review of knowledge, intellectual club "What? Where? When?" and others, children's research projects, out-of-school activities of a cognitive orientation (student conferences, intellectual marathons, etc.), school museum-club, etc. Independent or managed project activity of younger students helps to realize their creative potential. Any attempts to thematically limit the project activity of students within the framework of the academic subject or organizational - within the framework of the lesson (mini-projects of students as a form of independent work) are a substitute for the ideas of using the project method in the educational process. Lesson time can be used to organize work on the definition of the thematic field, problem and goal of the project (projects) of students, as well as to present the results of the project (projects). Each student implements their experience in the project by doing or participating in group projects at least once a year. Therefore, in different age groups, students need to be offered several options for organizing work on a project, for example: as part of a special training module; within the framework of imitation of project activities of students (for example, outside the lesson); while children are working on a real project.

The organization of extracurricular activities within the framework of the social direction can be based on socially useful activities. Forms of organization of the social direction: work within the framework of the project "Improvement of the school territory"; work on landscaping the classroom, school; organization of duty in the classroom; career guidance conversations, meetings with representatives of different professions; exhibitions of crafts and children's creativity; labor landings, subbotniks; social trials (initiative participation of the child in social events organized by adults); collective creative work; social and educational projects; role-playing productive games ("Post Office", "City of Masters", "Factory"), etc.

The social direction can also be focused on the patriotic education of students and be implemented through forms: search and research work in archives (family, school) and museum funds, etc., meetings with veterans, lessons of courage, watching patriotic films, thematic gatherings, creative competitions (songs, drawings, photographs, etc.), military and sports holidays ("Zarnitsa", "Young Rescuer", etc.), etc. Volunteer activity: patronage.

When organizing extracurricular activities of students, an educational institution uses the possibilities of educational institutions of additional education for children, organizations of culture and sports. Currently, there are four main models for organizing extracurricular activities in a comprehensive school.

The first model is characterized by a random set of circles, sections, clubs, the work of which is not always combined with each other, the connections with school-wide life are also situational and fragmentary. All extracurricular work and extracurricular activities of the school are completely dependent on the available human and material resources; strategic line of development of the organization of children's activities in the afternoon is not adjusted. Unfortunately, so far this is the most common model. But even this option of organizing extracurricular activities at school makes some sense, since it contributes to the employment of children and the definition of the spectrum of their extracurricular interests.

The second model is distinguished by the internal organization of each of the structures of the educational system available at the school, although a single system is not yet fully functioning. Nevertheless, in such models there are original forms of work that unite both children and adults (associations, creative laboratories, "expeditions", hobby centers, etc.). Clubs, circles, studios similar in profile can be combined into club centers operating according to a single program. However, these centers exist in the school in isolation; connections with general school work are also fragmentary. Quite often, in such schools, the field of additional education becomes an open search area in the process of updating the content of basic education, a kind of reserve and an experimental laboratory.

The third model for organizing extracurricular activities can be built on the basis of close interaction between a general education school and one or more institutions of additional education for children or a cultural institution - a center for children's creativity, a club at the place of residence, sports or music school, a library, a theater, a museum, etc. Such cooperation should be carried out on a regular basis. A school and a specialized institution, as a rule, develop a joint program of activities, which largely determines the content of extracurricular activities in a given school.

The fourth model of organization of extracurricular activities in a modern school involves a deep integration of basic and additional education of children. The definition of the content of their activities and ways of organizing it is based on common conceptual ideas that ensure the development of the institution as a whole. This is an educational complex, a school-club, a communal-type school. The number of hours allocated for extracurricular activities, the educational institution determines independently, based on the need to ensure the achievement of the planned results of the implementation of the main educational program of primary general education and based on the requests of students, parents (legal representatives), as well as available personnel, material and technical and other conditions

The occupancy of groups for extracurricular activities should not exceed 25 people.

The duration of extracurricular activities depends on age and type of activity. In grade 1, the duration of extracurricular activities is:

- 35 minutes, if the lessons are paired - 70 minutes plus a break of at least 10 minutes for children to relax and ventilate the premises.

The duration of such activities as reading, music lessons, drawing, modeling, needlework, quiet games should be no more than 50 minutes a day for students in grades 1-2 ... In music classes,

it is recommended to use more elements of rhythm and choreography. TV shows and movies should not be watched more than twice a week with a viewing time limit of up to 1 hour for students in grades 1-3.

The hours allotted for extracurricular activities (*up to 10 hours per week per class-set*) are used to conduct training courses that provide for the various interests and needs of students, including ethno-cultural and regional ones. It is not recommended for a child to attend extracurricular activities in more than 3 (three) children's associations.

Class	Direction of extracurricular activities	Name of the program, form of implementation	Number of study hours per week for 1 study group	Number of groups	FULL NAME. teacher
1a	Sports and health Telnoe	"Mini football" Section	2	1	Physical education teacher
		"Grow up healthy" circle	1	1	teacher of the beginning classes
	general intellectual	"Funny English"	1	1	foreign language teacher
		"I am a researcher" circle	1	1	teacher of the beginning classes
		"Children's Rhetoric" circle	1	1	teacher of the beginning classes
	Spiritual and moral	"My land" elective	1	1	Orthodox culture teacher
		Folklore Studio	1	1	music teacher
	Civil patriotic	Circle "Young Rescuer"	1	1	Educational psychologist
	General cultural	Circle "Paper-plastic"	1	1	labor education teacher
	TOTAL		10 hours		

Sample plan for extracurricular activities

Directions of extracurricular activities	1 class	Grade 2	3rd grade	4th grade
Sports and recreation	3	3	3	3
Spiritual and moral	2	2	2	2
Social	1	1	1	1
general intellectual	3	3	3	3
general cultural	1	1	1	1
Total	10	10	10	10

An approximate detailed plan for extracurricular activities for 1st grades:

The problem of using the free time of the younger generation for the purpose of comprehensive education and development has always been urgent for society. The upbringing of

children occurs at any time of their activity. However, it is most productive to carry out this upbringing in free time from training. Thus, the extracurricular activities of younger students should be aimed at their cultural and creative activities and spiritual and moral potential, a high level of self-awareness, discipline, and the ability to make the right moral choice. The school should create conditions for extracurricular activities of students and the organization of additional education. The entire system of school work in this area is designed to provide an opportunity to:

➤ *free choice by children of programs, associations that are close to them by nature, meet their internal needs;*

➤ *help to satisfy educational needs, to feel successful, to realize and develop their talents and abilities.*

➤ *become active in solving life and social problems, be able to take responsibility for your choice;*

➤ *be an active citizen of your country, able to love and protect nature, take an active life position in the struggle for peace on Earth, understand and accept ecological culture.*

➤ *The educational result of extracurricular activities is the direct spiritual and moral acquisition of the child due to his participation in one form or another of extracurricular activities.*

➤ *The educational effect of extracurricular activities is the influence of one or another spiritual and moral acquisition on the process of development of the child's personality (consequence of the result).*

CONCLUSION

In the work the extracurricular activities of schoolchildren are a set of all types of schoolchildren's activities, in which, in accordance with the main educational program of an educational institution, the tasks of education and socialization, development of interests, and the formation of universal educational activities are solved. Extracurricular activities are an integral part of the educational process at school and allow you to fully implement the requirements of the federal state educational standard (FSES) of primary general education. The features of this component of the educational process are providing students with the opportunity of a wide range of activities aimed at their development; as well as the independence of the educational institution in the process of filling extracurricular activities with specific content.

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